

A TRANSFORMATION DOMAIN DESCRIPTION FOR NONLINEAR PARTIAL DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Transfer function models for the description of physical systems with distributed parameters have recently been introduced to the field of multidimensional digital signal processing. They are an extension of the transfer functions description for one-dimensional systems and provide an alternative to the conventional representation by partial differential equations. Transfer function models are the starting point for the development of efficient discrete algorithms that are suitable for computer implementation. This paper extends the presented transformation domain description to nonlinear systems. A suitable choice of the integral transformations for the independent variables allows to treat certain types of nonlinearities in a similar way as for linear multidimensional systems.

1 Introduction

A transformation domain description for linear partial differential equations has recently been introduced [1]. The key issue is the choice of suitable integral transformations for the time and space variable. The time variable is transformed by the Laplace transformation in a similar way as for ordinary differential equations. The space variables in one, two, or three dimensions are transformed in a similar way by the so-called Sturm-Liouville transformation. The result is a transfer function description of initial-boundary value problems. It is suitable for the construction of discrete-time discrete-space algorithms for the numerical simulation of multidimensional (MD) systems. Examples for applications in heat transfer, electromagnetics, and elasticity theory have been given in [1, 2]. However, similar as for one-dimensional systems, the application of transformation domain descriptions has been confined to linear MD systems.

The numerical solution of nonlinear partial differential equations is usually done by traditional methods like finite difference or finite element methods [3, 4]. Integral transformation methods for linear and nonlinear

systems have been introduced in [7, 8]. Recently, also approaches according to the MD wave digital principle have been proposed [5].

Here, we extend the transformation domain description for linear MD systems to nonlinear partial differential equations (PDEs), where the coefficients of the PDE depend on the current value of the solution. It is shown, that application of the Sturm-Liouville transformation turns the nonlinear PDE into a set of coupled nonlinear ordinary differential equations, which can be solved by standard methods for numerical integration.

Section 2 describes the class of multidimensional (MD) systems under consideration. Section 3 reviews briefly the transformation domain description for the linear case. The extensions to nonlinear source terms and to nonlinear spatial differentiation operators are given in section 4.

2 Problem Description

We consider MD systems which are described by PDEs of the general form

$$\begin{aligned} D\{y(\mathbf{x}, t)\} + L\{y(\mathbf{x}, t)\} &= v(\mathbf{x}, t, y), & \mathbf{x} \in V \\ \mathbf{y}(\mathbf{x}, 0) &= \mathbf{0}, & \mathbf{x} \in V \\ f_b\{y(\mathbf{x}, t)\} &= 0, & \mathbf{x} \in \partial V. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The vector of space coordinates $\mathbf{x}$ is defined on a bounded domain V . t is the time coordinate with $t > 0$. $y(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the response of the system. $v(\mathbf{x}, t, y)$ is an excitation or source function. Its values may depend on the current response $y(\mathbf{x}, t)$. $D\{y(\mathbf{x}, t)\}$ is a linear differential operator with respect to time. It consists of a linear combination of time derivatives of $y(\mathbf{x}, t)$. For simplicity, we consider here only derivatives up to second order

$$D\{y\} = a_2 \ddot{y} + a_1 \dot{y} + a_0 y, \quad (2)$$

where $\dot{y}$ and $\ddot{y}$ denote first and second order time derivatives. The coefficients a_i , $i = 0, 1, 2$ do not depend on time and space.

$L\{y(\mathbf{x}, t)\}$ is partial differential operator with respect to the space coordinate $\mathbf{x}$. We consider the cases where L is either linear and self-adjoint or where L is a non-linear operator.

The initial conditions for the temporal differential operator D are specified by the time derivatives of $y(\mathbf{x}, t)$ for $t = 0$. Their values $y(\mathbf{x}, 0), \dot{y}(\mathbf{x}, 0), \dots$ are contained in the vector $\mathbf{y}(\mathbf{x}, 0)$.

The boundary conditions for the spatial differential operator L are given in terms of the function f_b , which specifies boundary conditions of the first, second or third kind on the surface ∂V of V . Only homogeneous initial and boundary conditions are considered here. Inhomogeneous initial and boundary conditions for linear MD systems have been treated in [1, 2].

3 Linear MD Systems

A detailed description of transfer function models for linear MD systems is given in [1, 2]. This section provides only a short review for the linear version of the initial-boundary value problem presented in section 2. Specifically, we assume in this section that the source function $v(\mathbf{x}, t)$ does not depend on the solution y and that the spatial differential operator L is linear and self-adjoint.

First we introduce an integral transformation for the space variable, the so called Sturm-Liouville (SL) transformation and some of its properties. Then we show how the SL transformation turns the initial-boundary value problem (1) for the time and space variable into a initial value problem for the time variable. A transfer function model is obtained by application of the Laplace transformation with respect to the time variable. Finally time discretization and inverse SL transformation result in a discrete algorithm suitable for computer implementation.

3.1 Sturm-Liouville Transformation

The transformation with respect to the space variable $\mathbf{x}$ is defined by

$$\mathcal{T}\{y(\mathbf{x}, t)\} = \bar{y}(\beta, t) = \int_V y(\mathbf{x}, t)K(\mathbf{x}, \beta) dV \quad (3)$$

with the spatial frequency variable β . It may also be written as a scalar product between $y(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and the transformation kernel $K(\mathbf{x}, \beta)$

$$\mathcal{T}\{y(\mathbf{x}, t)\} = \bar{y}(\beta, t) = \langle y(\mathbf{x}, t), K(\mathbf{x}, \beta) \rangle. \quad (4)$$

The scalar product between two real-valued space dependent functions $u_1(\mathbf{x})$ and $u_2(\mathbf{x})$ is given by

$$\langle u_1(\mathbf{x}), u_2(\mathbf{x}) \rangle = \int_V u_1(\mathbf{x})u_2(\mathbf{x}) dV. \quad (5)$$

Application of the SL transformation $\mathcal{T}$ to the initial-boundary value problem (1) is straightforward

with the exception of the spatial differential operator L . Its transform yields the scalar product $\langle L\{y(\mathbf{x}, t)\}, K(\mathbf{x}, \beta) \rangle$. To express this scalar product by the the transform $\bar{y}(\beta, t)$, we use the property that L is self-adjoint and that (1) has homogeneous boundary conditions. Then the following Greens formula holds

$$\langle L\{y(\mathbf{x})\}, K(\mathbf{x}, \beta) \rangle = \langle y(\mathbf{x}), L\{K(\mathbf{x}, \beta)\} \rangle. \quad (6)$$

So far, the transformation kernel $K(\mathbf{x}, \beta)$ is not yet determined. Now, we demand that $K(\mathbf{x}, \beta)$ satisfies the following time-independent boundary value problem

$$-\beta^m K(\mathbf{x}, \beta) + L\{K(\mathbf{x}, \beta)\} = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$f_b\{K(\mathbf{x}, \beta)\} = 0, \quad (8)$$

where m is the highest order of the spatial differentiation in L .

Boundary-value problems of this type are well known as *Sturm-Liouville problems* [6]. They have the following useful properties: Nontrivial solutions exist only for discrete values $\beta_\mu, \mu = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ of the frequency variable and the corresponding solutions $K(\mathbf{x}, \beta_\mu)$ are mutually orthogonal. β_μ and $K(\mathbf{x}, \beta_\mu)$ constitute the eigenvalues and eigenfunctions of the Sturm-Liouville problem.

With the Greens formula (6) and the Sturm-Liouville problem (7,8) it is easy to show that the SL transform of $L\{y(\mathbf{x}, t)\}$ can be expressed by the transform of $y(\mathbf{x}, t)$

$$\langle L\{y(\mathbf{x}, t)\}, K(\mathbf{x}, \beta_\mu) \rangle = \beta_\mu^m \bar{y}(\beta_\mu, t). \quad (9)$$

Since the eigenfunctions $K(\mathbf{x}, \beta_\mu)$ are orthogonal, the inverse SL transformation is given by a generalized Fourier series [7, 8] as

$$\mathcal{T}^{-1}\{\bar{y}(\beta_\mu, t)\} = y(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_{\mu=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{N_\mu} \bar{y}(\beta_\mu, t)K(\mathbf{x}, \beta_\mu). \quad (10)$$

The normalization factor N_μ is the squared l_2 norm of the transformation kernel $K(\mathbf{x}, \beta_\mu)$.

3.2 Initial Value Problem

Application of the SL transformation (4) with the spatial differentiation property (9) turns the initial-boundary value problem (1) into an initial value problem

$$\begin{aligned} D\{\bar{y}(\beta_\mu, t)\} + \beta_\mu^m \bar{y}(\beta_\mu, t) &= \bar{v}(\beta_\mu, t), & \mathbf{x} \in V \\ \bar{y}(\beta_\mu, 0) &= \mathbf{0}, & \mathbf{x} \in V. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

It constitutes a system of decoupled ordinary differential equations (ODEs) for the time variable and can be solved by standard numerical routines.

3.3 Transfer Function Model

However, more insight is gained by exploiting the fact that $D\{y\}$ according to (2) is a operator with constant

coefficients. In this case, the one-sided Laplace transformation $\mathcal{L}\{\bar{y}(\beta, t)\} = \bar{Y}(\beta, s)$ with respect to the time variable has the differentiation theorem

$$\mathcal{L}\{D\{\bar{y}(\beta, t)\}\} = \gamma^2(s)\bar{Y}(\beta, s). \quad (12)$$

$\gamma^2(s)$ follows from (2)

$$\gamma^2(s) = a_2s^2 + a_1s + a_0 \quad (13)$$

and s is the complex frequency for the time variable. Note, that (12) holds only for homogeneous initial conditions according to (1).

Thus, application of the Laplace transformation turns the initial value problem (11) into a purely algebraic equation. Solving it for the transform $\bar{Y}(\beta_\mu, s)$ of the solution yields the transfer function model

$$\bar{Y}(\beta_\mu, s) = \bar{G}(\beta_\mu, s)\bar{V}(\beta_\mu, s) \quad (14)$$

with the transfer function

$$\bar{G}(\beta_\mu, s) = \frac{1}{\gamma^2(s) + \beta_\mu^m} \quad (15)$$

The transfer function $\bar{G}(\beta_\mu, s)$ is a transformation domain description of the linear version of the PDE (1). It represents a linear MD system in the same way as the conventional Laplace transfer function represents a lumped parameter system given by a constant coefficient ordinary differential equation.

3.4 Discretization

The transfer function description (14) is the starting point for the discretization with signal processing methods. Conventional analog-to-discrete transformations turn the transfer function $\bar{G}(\beta_\mu, s)$ into a discrete-time transfer function $\bar{G}^h(\beta_\mu, z)$. It corresponds to a discrete-time difference equation via the z -transformation. Since the spatial frequency variable β_μ is already discrete, we obtain a fully discrete system representation as a parallel arrangement of discrete-time systems. Details are given e.g. in [2].

4 Nonlinear MD Systems

Now we generalize these results to PDEs with nonlinear MD Systems. At first we consider PDEs with linear differential operators but with nonlinear excitation. Then we turn to PDEs with nonlinear coefficients in the spatial differential operator. It turns out that that transform domain description introduced for linear systems can also be applied to these kinds of nonlinear MD systems. Finally a special case of nonlinear excitation is considered.

4.1 Nonlinear Excitations

In this section L is still linear and self-adjoint but the excitation $v(\mathbf{x}, t, y)$ depends on the solution $y(\mathbf{x}, t)$. The SL transformation for this problem is determined in the same way as for linear systems in section 3.1. However the application of the SL transformation to the initial-boundary value problem (1) no longer yields a system of decoupled ODEs as in (11). Instead we obtain at first

$$D\{\bar{y}(\beta_\mu, t)\} + \beta_\mu^m \bar{y}(\beta_\mu, t) = \langle v(\mathbf{x}, t, y), K(\mathbf{x}, \beta_\mu) \rangle. \quad (16)$$

To express the term on the right hand side by $\bar{y}(\beta_\nu, t)$ instead of $y(\mathbf{x}, t)$, we make use of the inverse SL transformation (10)

$$v(\mathbf{x}, t, y) = v\left(\mathbf{x}, t, \sum_{\nu=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{N_\nu} \bar{y}(\beta_\nu, t) K(\mathbf{x}, \beta_\nu)\right). \quad (17)$$

Thus $\langle v(\mathbf{x}, t, y), K(\mathbf{x}, \beta_\mu) \rangle$ depends for each eigenvalue μ also on the other eigenvalues $\nu \neq \mu$. This fact is emphasized by the short hand notation

$$\langle v(\mathbf{x}, t, y), K(\mathbf{x}, \beta_\mu) \rangle = \bar{v}_\mu(\bar{y}(\beta_\nu, t)). \quad (18)$$

Obviously the system of ODEs is now coupled by the term at the right hand side

$$D\{\bar{y}(\beta_\mu, t)\} + \beta_\mu^m \bar{y}(\beta_\mu, t) = \bar{v}_\mu(\bar{y}(\beta_\nu, t)). \quad (19)$$

In general there is no simple transfer function model as in (14) and thus no time discretization by z -transformation methods. However the coupled system of ODEs can be solved for $\bar{y}(\beta_\mu, t)$ by standard numerical routines. Finally the solution $y(\mathbf{x}, t)$ results from an approximate numerical evaluation of the inverse SL transformation (10).

4.2 Nonlinear Spatial Differentiation Operators

Next we consider PDEs with nonlinear spatial differentiation operators. In this section the excitation $v(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is independent of y but the operator $L\{y\}$ contains coefficients which depend on y . To arrive at a system of ODEs similar to the case of nonlinear excitations, we need some assumptions on the nature of the nonlinearity of the spatial differentiation operator. The first assumption is that $L\{y\}$ can be decomposed into two linear and self-adjoint operators $L_0\{y\}$ and $L_1\{y\}$ and into a nonlinear coefficient $a(y)$

$$L\{y\} = L_0\{y\} + a(y)L_1\{y\}. \quad (20)$$

Furthermore $L_0\{y\}$ and $L_1\{y\}$ shall be of a similar structure. That is $L_0\{y\}$ satisfies the Sturm-Liouville problem (7,8) and $L_1\{y\}$ satisfies a similar Sturm-Liouville problem

$$-\eta_\mu^n K(\mathbf{x}, \eta_\mu) + L_1\{K(\mathbf{x}, \eta_\mu)\} = 0 \quad (21)$$

$$f_b\{K(\mathbf{x}, \eta_\mu)\} = 0, \quad (22)$$

with the same eigenfunctions K but possibly different eigenvalues η_μ as in (7,8). n is the order of the highest derivative in L_1 . Spatial differentiation operators of this structure are frequently found in physical problems.

For the nonlinear coefficient $a(y)$, we assume the following form

$$a(y) = \int_V b(y(\xi)) d\xi = \bar{a}(\bar{y}(\beta_\nu, t)), \quad (23)$$

where the inverse SL transformation has been applied as in (17). $b(y)$ is an arbitrary nonlinear function of y . The meaning of (23) is that $a(y)$ is constant with respect to the space coordinates. As a simple example for such a coefficient $a(y)$ consider

$$a(y) = \int_V y^2(\xi, t) d\xi = \sum_{\nu=1}^{\infty} \bar{y}^2(\beta_\nu, t) \frac{1}{N_\nu} = \bar{a}(\bar{y}(\beta_\nu, t))$$

Since $a(y)$ does not depend on the space coordinates, we can show that

$$\langle a(y)L_1\{y(\mathbf{x})\}, K(\mathbf{x}, \beta_\mu) \rangle = \bar{a}(\bar{y}(\beta_\nu, t)) \eta_\mu^n \bar{y}(\beta_\nu, t). \quad (24)$$

Now we can apply the SL transformation to (1) and obtain

$$D\{\bar{y}(\beta_\mu, t)\} + (\beta_\mu^m + \bar{a}(\bar{y}(\beta_\nu, t))\eta_\mu^n) \bar{y}(\beta_\mu, t) = \bar{v}(\beta_\nu, t). \quad (25)$$

Similar as in the case of nonlinear excitations we get a system of ODEs that are coupled by the coefficients $\bar{a}(\bar{y}(\beta_\nu, t))$. The solution $y(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is obtained by the same numerical procedure as above.

4.3 Pointwise Excitation

It is not always necessary to find the solution of a nonlinear MD system by numerical integration of coupled ODEs. This is demonstrated shortly for the case of a pointwise nonlinear excitation. This is a typical case for the excitation of vibrating bodies like bowed and hammered strings, gongs, bells, etc.

We return to (16) and restrict the excitation to a fixed point $\mathbf{x}_e$ in V

$$v(\mathbf{x}, t, y) = \delta_0(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_e) v(t, y). \quad (26)$$

$\delta_0(\mathbf{x})$ denotes a spatial impulse function in V . In this case $\bar{v}_\mu(\bar{y}(\beta_\nu, t))$ in (18) reduces to

$$\bar{v}_\mu(\bar{y}(\beta_\nu, t)) = v(t, y)K(\mathbf{x}_e, \beta_\mu). \quad (27)$$

Thus the system of ODEs in (18) does not depend on $K(\mathbf{x}, \beta_\nu)$ for $\nu \neq \mu$. It can be discretized in the same way as described for the transfer function models in section 3.4. The application of such a MD system for digital sound synthesis with nonlinear excitations is described in a companion paper [9].

5 Conclusions

The analysis of physical systems with distributed parameters leads to a description by PDEs with respect to time and space. For linear systems there exists also a transformation domain description. It allows to characterize MD systems by transfer functions in a similar way as for one-dimensional systems. To this end, suitable integral transformation for the time and space coordinates have to be applied.

In this contribution has been shown how the spatial transformation for linear systems can also be applied to PDEs with nonlinear coefficients. The resulting transformation domain description is a system of coupled nonlinear ordinary differential equations. They can be solved by standard numerical routines. For special cases of nonlinear excitations it is also possible to proceed to a transfer function model similar to the linear case.

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